

Alignment of QTLs/major genes for RYMV and blast resistance on rice chromosome 12. Loci were detected using DH lines derived from two indica/japonica F₁ hybrids (IR64/Azucena and IRAT 177/Apura). Vertical dashed line indicates position of RG869 marker, which separates *Pi4* and *Pi6* in other studies. The peaks observed on each side of the line could correspond to these two genes.

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Characterization of a pathogenesis-related gene family induced in rice infected with *Magnaporthe grisea*

J. D. McGee, Botany and Plant Pathology Department, Purdue University (PU), West Lafayette, IN 47907, USA; N. J. Talbot, T. Bhargava, and J. E. Hamer, Biology Department, PU; and T. K. Hodges, Botany and Plant Pathology Department, PU

Fungal pathogens, such as *Magnaporthe grisea* and *Rhizoctonia solani* can cause significant yield losses. Increased disease resistance can be obtained in plants transformed with genes encoding known antifungal proteins, such as the hydrolytic enzymes chitinase and β -1,3-glucanase

(Jach et al 1995, Zhu et al 1994). We isolated a *M. grisea*-induced promoter that was later used to drive antifungal genes in rice to suppress the effects of fungal infection.

Rice cDNAs, whose genes exhibited elevated expression during rice blast infection, have been isolated through differential screening (Talbot et al 1993). One of these cDNAs, MAG-7, was chosen as a source of the *M. grisea*-induced promoter. MAG-7 was found to share homology with a known class of PR proteins (PR-10 proteins) found in various plants (van Loon et al 1994).

Southern blot hybridization of rice genomic DNA (varieties Co 39, IR36, and IR54) probed with the MAG-7 cDNA indicated that these varieties contain multiple (2-5) copies of the MAG-7 gene

1. Northern blot analyses comparing the presence of different rice mRNA transcripts at various times following *Magnaporthe grisea* infection. 10- μ g samples of total RNA isolated either from uninfected 3-wk-old Co 39 seedlings (0 h) or from 3-wk-old seedlings infected for 12, 18, 24, 36, 48, 72, or 144 h were hybridized to different rice PR-10 probes. (a) Total RNA hybridized with a 814-bp nonspecific probe from a PR-10a cDNA, which shares homology with all three rice PR-10 genes. (b) Total RNA hybridized to a 198-bp probe derived from the 5' untranslated region of the PR-10a gene. (c) Total RNA hybridized to a 230-bp probe derived from the 3' untranslated region of the PR-10b gene. (d) Total RNA hybridized to a 231-bp probe derived from the 5' untranslated region of the PR-10c gene. The intensity of chloroplast 23S rRNA in b, c, and d shows similar amounts of RNA loaded onto gels.

per haploid genome. A 16-kb genomic clone isolated from a Co 39 genomic library was found to contain three copies of the MAG-7 gene (named rice PR-10a, rice PR-10b, and rice PR-10c). Rice PR-10a, sequenced in its entirety, including about 1.4 kb of the 5' promoter region, shared 100% homology with the MAG-7 cDNA. The rice PR-10b and PR-10c genes have been partially sequenced.

We constructed gene-specific probes to observe transcriptional differences among the three rice PR-10 genes in Northern blots of total RNA isolated from Co 39 seedling leaves at 0, 12, 18, 24, 36, 48, 72, and 144 h after *M. grisea* infection (Fig. 1).

Transcripts of rice PR-10a were induced from a low basal level within 12 h following *M. grisea* infection, with increasing accumulation overtime. *M. grisea* also enhanced transcripts of rice PR-10b, for which induction became strongly visible 48 h after inoculation. Unlike rice PR-10a and rice PR-10b, rice PR-10c exhibited no signs of induction by *M. grisea* in RNA samples isolated from infected rice leaves throughout the 144 h.

Tissue prints of *M. grisea*-infected Co 39 leaves were made using the PR-10a gene-specific probe (Fig. 2). Hybridization of the rice PR-10a probe occurred only at the infection site, illustrating that *M. grisea* induces the rice PR-10a transcript in a localized fashion.

2. Tissue print illustrating the localized transcription of the rice PR-10a gene during *Magnaporthe grisea* infection. A 2-wk-old (Co 39) rice seedling was inoculated with two adjacent 20- μ l drops of *M. grisea* conidial suspension (0.4% gelatin; 1,000 conidia drop⁻¹). Following 72 h of incubation, the seedling was pressed onto a nylon membrane and hybridized to an antisense RNA probe specific for the rice PR-10a transcript. Inset photo: a 4X magnification of the infection site.

Barley genes encoding class II chitinase, class II β 1,3-gluconase, and Type-I ribosome-inactivating protein (Jach et al 1995) will be introduced into rice via *Agrobacterium tumefaciens* transformation to study their ability to control fungal diseases. Both the rice PR-10a promoter and the constitutively expressed ubiquitin promoter will be used to drive each of these genes; the effectiveness of both promoters will be compared.

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Genes controlling field resistance to blast in Japanese upland rice detected using RFLP markers

S. Fukuoka, K. Okuno, National Institute of Agrobiological Resources, Tsukuba, Ibaraki 305, Japan; M. Kawase, Shikoku National Agricultural Experiment Station, Zentsuji, Kagawa 765, Japan; K. Miura, Hokkaido National Agricultural Experiment Station, Sapporo, Hokkaido 062, Japan; and S. Kiyosawa, Tsukuba International Agricultural Training Center, Tsukuba, Ibaraki 305, Japan

After observing the rapid breakdown of vertical resistance genes to blast, such as *Pi-k*, rice breeders are now developing

breeding lines with field resistance to blast. Field resistance is defined as the resistance that allows effective control of a parasite under natural field conditions. Japanese upland rice varieties are potential gene donors for field resistance. Studies using linkage analysis with conventional genetic markers have pointed to several different loci controlling field resistance to blast (Goto 1970, Shinoda et al 1971, Higashi and Saito 1985).

We studied the chromosomal location of genes controlling field resistance to blast in Japanese upland rice using restriction fragment length polymorphism (RFLP) markers.

RFLP is frequently detected among Japanese varieties. About 40% of RFLP

markers located on the rice genetic linkage map revealed RFLP between lowland and upland rice varieties using DNA probes polymorphic between lowland and upland varieties.

Field resistance to leaf blast was genetically analyzed. Three hundred twelve F₃ lines from a cross between Nipponbare (moderately susceptible, lowland) and Owarihatamochi (resistant, upland) were field-tested for resistance to blast. Of these, 27 F₃ lines expressed resistance equivalent to that of Owarihatamochi while 27 lines were susceptible. Total DNA was extracted from leaves of resistant and susceptible F₃ lines and their parents. Using 138 RFLP markers, we determined the relationship between